

MICROBIOLOGICAL BIOLOGICAL PRODUCTS FOR LEGUMES

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Abstract. *Recently, many scientific studies have focused on the study of biological nitrogen fixation. Many biological products for legumes have been obtained on the basis of symbiotic nitrogen-fixing microorganisms. Scientific experiments in this field have shown that nitrogen-fixation microorganisms serve to increase the productivity of legumes and enrich soils with biological nitrogen.*

Nodule bacteria of the genus Rhizobium in symbiosis with legumes absorb nitrogen from the atmosphere and provide the plant with the necessary amounts of biological nitrogen. As a result of this process, the growth of vegetative mass in plants increases by its length, the weight of the grain mass increases, and as a result, their products are considered biologically pure products.

Keywords: *microbial-plant interactions, rhizobial symbiosis, biological products.*

Introduction. Currently, huge amounts of money are being spent in agriculture to save on the cost of using mineral fertilizers. An alternative to save money on mineral nitrogen is the use of products obtained on the basis of symbiotic microorganisms. One of the urgent problems in obtaining biologically pure products is the use of biologics based on nodule bacteria.

Nodule bacteria of the genus Rhizobium, which are in a symbiotic relationship with legumes, have the property of forming nodules in plant roots and carrying out a reversible reaction of converting molecular nitrogen from the atmosphere into ammonia in nodule bacteria cells. In the nodule genome, in the presence of a complex of enzymes nitrogenase, dinitrogenase (MoFe protein) and dinitrogenase reductase (Fe protein), complex biochemical reactions are carried out and as a result, molecular nitrogen from the atmosphere turns into the form of NH₂ in the bacterial cell, an accessible and easy form for assimilation by the plant. In this way, plants easily absorb biological nitrogen. This ability of nodule bacteria provides the basis for using them for the preparation of biological products. Obtaining biological products based on nitrogen-fixing bacteria, and their use in agriculture, reduce the cost of producing nitrogen-containing mineral fertilizers, as well as a sharp reduction in their use in agriculture and improving the quality of the products obtained. Plants grown with biologics and without mineral fertilizers are considered biologically pure products. The use of biological products in agriculture is an alternative way for plants to assimilate nitrogen.

As a result of biological nitrogen fixation, legumes accumulate up to 600 kg of nitrogen per hectare in the soil [1]. The amount of nitrogen that can accumulate in the soil significantly exceeds the needs of legumes and provides subsequent crops with a nitrogen-binding substance [1]. Therefore, the cultivation of legumes, which fully realize their symbiotic potential, makes it possible to replace a significant part of mineral fertilizers for plants in the present and subsequent years by enriching the soil with nitrogen.

The effectiveness of biologics depends on the composition of strains, as well as on soil conditions, the presence of native nodule bacteria in the soil, the ability of legumes to enter into symbiosis and use biological nitrogen instead of mineral nitrogen. Under normal conditions, the

process of biological nitrogen fixation may be lower than the expected result, this case requires the application of mineral fertilizers to legumes and other plants in the required amount. To limit these cases, many researchers [1,2,3] in the conclusions of their experiments reported vaccination of legumes with nodule bacteria before planting, which leads to activation of effective symbiosis and increased specificity.

Vaccination of plants with biological products is the reason that they dominate soil bacteria with low productivity and that they make the nitrogen fixation process effective. The possibilities of symbiosis do not depend on the genes located on chromosomes in the bacterial genome, but on the genes contained in symbiotic mega-plasmids, which have a very large size (1800 bp) in their genome [4]. They can actively exchange with cells of natural rhizobial bacteria existing in the soil, transporting genes in a horizontal state, such changes cause a loss of the ability to nitrogen fixation. In the soil, nodule bacteria cannot absorb nitrogen from the atmosphere in a free state, their survival outside plants, their ability to symbiose is realized only through the plant, therefore the symbiotic effect of natural strains is low, which does not mean that their ability to virulence disappears. When legumes are inoculated with microbiological preparations, in the field they are subjected to strong competition from natural bacteria living in the soil and cause a decrease in their effectiveness.

In some soils for soybean cultivation, including in Uzbekistan, the absence of specific bacteria for this legume plant is characteristic. Therefore, these bacterial cultures, unlike other crops, differ in the effectiveness of inoculation with microbiological preparations and provide increased plant nutrition.

The specifics of nitrogen-fixing symbiosis

Certain species (sometimes individual strains) of nodule bacteria manifest themselves only when interacting with certain species of host plants (sometimes individual genotypes) [5,6,7]. Such specificity cannot be changed by any physiological influences, since it is determined by genetic mechanisms, and therefore only by changing the genotype of nodule bacteria strains can their relationship with the host plant be changed. The main task of modern science in this field is to study the mechanisms that carry out the symbiosis of legume and nodule bacteria, which absorb nitrogen, in a unique way. Bacteria and plants are able to recognize each other with the help of their signaling molecules in the absence of sensory organs. In symbiosis, their interaction begins with the fact that bacteria receive signals from the plant – the plant begins with the release of flavonoid molecules characteristic of its species. This signal binds to bacterial receptors, activating gene transcription for the development of nodules that are inactive in the absence of bacterial genes in the plant [5,6,7,8,9]. As a result of the expression of these Nod factor genes, the enzymatic synthesis of chitin signaling molecules occurs: nodules have high activity when they are isolated. The set of genes that determine the production of Nod factors has so far been very well characterized [5,6,9]. Therefore, by manipulating them using molecular genetics methods, it is possible to change the spectrum of Nod factors produced by bacteria, and as a result, change the specificity of interaction, thereby regulating the colonization of legumes with the necessary strains of nodule bacteria.

A detailed study of the mechanisms of interaction between plants and bacteria opens up opportunities to increase the competitiveness of industrial strains, as well as to create the most specific varietal-strain compounds to achieve maximum efficiency of symbiotic nitrogen fixation of plants and microbes vaccinated in the field.

Production of microbiological preparations

Considering the specifics of the interaction of plants and microorganisms, the development of the production of microbiological preparations should also be carried out on the basis of the regional principle of general control. In each region, it is advisable to produce its own line of raw materials for legumes (there may be more than 20 species in these rows). The current level of scientific development recommends selecting strains of microorganisms not only for a specific plant, but also for individual varieties that are sensitive to vaccination. Therefore, when creating biological products, the areas for legumes should flexibly respond to annual changes in their composition.

Conclusion. The most important factor in the effectiveness of interaction in the symbiotic process is the plant's response to symbiosis, that is, the susceptibility of plants to vaccination with microbiological preparations. By creating varieties with this feature in mind, we increase their ability to interact with the entire complex of beneficial microflora and make them as self-sufficient as possible - we optimize the absorption of nitrogen and phosphorus substances, provide protection from many pathogens, various biotic and abiotic stresses, including drought.

At the same time, we consider it appropriate to note that the use of symbiotic nitrogen fixation, which has great innovative potential, does not exclude an increase in the availability of nitrogen fertilizers for agricultural producers in Uzbekistan. In other words, the optimal way to develop the agroindustrial complex of Uzbekistan, in our opinion, is a rational combination of the use of biological and mineral nitrogen.

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